

Culture Fresh Water and Marine Water Rotifer for Ornamental Fishes

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Introduction

The Latin term for "wheel-bearer" is where the name "Rotifer" comes from. The phylum Rotifer includes the tiny organisms known as rotifers (*Brachionus spp.*), which are found in freshwater and marine environments. The food of rotifers often consists of dead or decomposing organic items, as well as unicellular algae and other phytoplankton that are the main producers in aquatic communities. Rotifers are primarily omnivorous, while some species have been found to engage in cannibalism. Some rotifers become their main consumers due to these eating behaviors. Rotifers move slowly and scatter evenly throughout the water columns, making them a popular live food for marine and ornamental fish. As a result of their size being suitable for larval fish as a beginning diet during early exogenous feeding, they are regarded as an essential forage zooplankton. They are the ideal size for the majority of demersal species, and they reproduce quickly. As a result, the larval tank is guaranteed to have a high density of feeding organisms, allowing slow-moving larvae to maximize development while using only the necessary amount of energy.

The nutrients that rotifers convey to the larvae are actually provided by the algae they ingest because they themselves lack any nutritional value. This crucial live food organism has been produced using a variety of culture methods. It takes a lot of labour to produce *Brachionus plicatilis* (Marine Rotifer). In contrast to *Brachionus rotundiformis*, which develops well even at temperatures of 28 °C or more, *Brachionus plicatilis* needs intensive care and its development rate begins to slow down above 26° C. *Brachionus plicatilis* consumes a variety of algae, including Chlorella, Scenedesmus, Nanochloropsis, Isochrysis, Monochrysis, Dunaliella, and others. Numerous

variables, including temperature, salinity, food quality and quantity, and overcrowding, affect the generation of rotifers. etc.

Zooplankton used for Live Feeding

- The success of rotifers as a culture organism are manifold,
 - Planktonic nature,
 - Tolerance to a wide range of environmental conditions,
 - High reproduction rate
 - Small size and slow swimming velocity make them a suitable prey for fish larvae that have just resorbed their yolk sac but cannot yet ingest the larger *Artemia* nauplii.
- Possibility of rearing these animals at very high densities (*i.e.*, Densities of 2000 animals /ml has been reported by Hirata (1979). Even at high densities, the animals reproduce rapidly and can thus contribute to the build-up of large quantities of live food in a very short period of time.

- Last, the filter-feeding nature of the rotifers facilitates the inclusion into their body tissues of specific nutrients essential for the larval predators.

Main Species of Rotifers

- Brachionus plicatilis*. (Marine Water)
- Brachionus rotundiformis*. (Marine Water)
- Brachionus calyciflorus*. (Fresh Water)

Optimum condition for growth

PARAMETER	OPTIMUM RANGE
Temperature	25-30°C
pH	7.5-8
Salinity	20-30 ppt
Ammonia	<1mg/l
D. 0	2-5 mg/l

Turbulence given by aeration- keeps rotifers and food particles in suspension.

Culture Methods

1. Stock cultures for inoculant or starter culture are maintained in 1–2-liter flasks.
2. Stock culture can be maintained on an algal diet of *Isochrysis galbana* at and a light cycle of 12 light: 12 darks
3. Culture should be restarted periodically, at least every month or more.

Culture Systems for Rotifers

1. Unit for culturing of food for *Brachionus*- Primary requirement for culture of rotifers is the feed. - *Chlorella*, bacteria and yeast.
2. Unit for *Brachionus* stock culture.
3. Mass culture Unit

Unit for *Brachionus* stock culture

- Collect rotifers from Brackish water bodies- 50 L of pond water filtered through filter of mesh size- 50-100mm .
- Examine under microscope., pick out rotifers using fine dropper and place in cavity block with 3.5 ml distilled water.
- *Chlorella* medium is put into cavity blocks.

- One rotifer is introduced into this cavity block, covered with glass plate, kept in diffused light.
- At every 12 hours, the medium is replaced with fresh chlorella and add live rotifer with eggs
- Gradually increase the culture volume to 25 ml in a 50 ml beaker and change the culture daily once.
- Use 50-70 mm size mesh to separate the rotifers, continue the process till the density reaches 50 numbers of rotifers per ml, and culture vol. is 500ml. Chlorella density may be 3-4 million cells/ml.

Mass culture Unit

Mass culture methods are of three types

1. Batch culture:

The population of culture vessel is entirely harvested at or near its peak density. Used as inoculum for other culture vessels, used for feeding in I-RT. Small to medium sized containers are used, kept indoors. After harvest the entire batch is discarded, then a fresh batch is started all over again. Filtered sea water is enriched with fertilisers such as urea, / amino sulphate and super phosphate, it is inoculated with Chlorella. Medium aerated, inoculated with rotifers once the suitable density of algae is reached. Rotifers grow and multiply, at density of 100-300 individual. /ml, they are harvested.

2. Semi- continuous culture:

Partial harvest is done at intervals. The harvested volume replaced by fresh medium to keep the growth going on. Large number of algae produced in outdoor tanks. Risk of contamination by other organisms and building up of metabolites.

3. Feedback culture:

Faecal and other particulate matters settled at the bottom of rotifer culture tanks are allowed to undergo bacterial decomposition which is used as a fertiliser for algae cultured in a separate tank.

Conclusion

Rotifers can be cultured in a variety of ways. Keep the water and culture containers clean. Ensure that bacteria and ciliates are under control. To keep the culture in growth phase, harvest every day. This review examines rotifer research trends and makes recommendations for what could be achieved with more work. In light of this, I provide the same sagacity that was first offered to me over 30 years ago (Donald Zinn, personal

communication). Consider studying rotifers if you want to learn more about an understudied group of invertebrates

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